

Oxalic acid – a new catalyst for the syntheses of dihydropyrimidinones in solvent-free condition[†]

Alok Kumar Mitra* and Sajal Kumar Banerjee

Department of Chemistry, University of Calcutta, Kolkata-700 09, India

E-mail : akmitra@cucc.ernet.in; a_k_mitra@hotmail.com Fax : 91-33-23519755

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High yielding and fast one-pot synthesis of 3,4-dihydropyrimidin-2(1H)-ones from β -ketoesters, urea and various aldehydes using oxalic acid as a catalyst in solvent-free condition under microwave irradiation is reported.

Dihydropyrimidinone derivatives¹ in recent days have exhibited important pharmacological activities as the antihypertensive agents, integral backbone of several calcium channel blockers, alpha-la-antagonists and neuropeptide Y (NPY) antagonists². Several recently³ isolated marine alkaloids with interesting biological activities also contain the dihydropyrimidinone-5-carboxylate core. Most notable among these are the batzelladine alkaloids which have been found to be potent HIVgp-120-CD4 inhibitors⁴. Therefore, many synthetic methods for preparing such compounds have been reported¹. The first synthesis was carried out by Biginelli⁵, which is a one-pot but low yielding (often 20–50%) condensation of ethyl acetoacetate with aldehydes and urea in the presence of strong mineral acid. However, serious drawbacks of Biginelli reaction are the use of strong acid as well as the low yields in the case of substituted aromatic and aliphatic aldehydes⁶. As Biginelli reaction has received renewed interest, several improved procedures have recently been reported^{7–13}. But these methods suffer from disadvantages like use of protic acids^{7,8}, strong Lewis acids^{7,9}, expensive lanthanide compounds^{10,11} and organic solvents^{9,12,13} which are generally toxic to living beings¹⁴.

In recent days, the growing interest in the application of "Microwave-induced Organic Reaction Enhancement" (MORE) chemistry is due to high reaction rates and formation of cleaner products¹⁵. The solvent-free¹⁶ condition is especially appealing for providing an eco-friendly system. In continuation of our ongoing programme¹⁷ to develop synthetic protocols utilizing microwave radiation under solvent-free conditions, we report herein the synthesis of a variety of 3,4-dihydropyrimidin-2(1H)-ones using oxalic acid as the catalyst in the condensation reaction of ethyl/methyl acetoacetate with urea and various aliphatic and aromatic

aldehydes under microwave irradiation in absence of any organic solvent. The reactions (Scheme 1) proceeded efficiently in high yields (79–92%) at ambient pressure in open vessels within a very short time (11–23 min) (Table 1). By conventional heating method (oil bath) at 110°, the reaction required 6 h for completion.

R¹ = Alkyl, Aryl

R² = Me, Et

Scheme 1

This procedure has the advantage that oxalic acid is easily available and inexpensive and the work-up is very simple as this acid is soluble in water. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first report of the synthesis of 3,4-dihydropyrimidin-2(1H)-ones using oxalic acid.

In conclusion, we have developed an efficient and expeditious microwave-assisted method of Biginelli reaction, exploiting oxalic acid as the catalyst.

Experimental

M.ps. were taken in open capillary on an electrically heated metal block and are uncorrected. The IR spectra were run on a Perkin-Elmer FT IR-RXI spectrophotometer using KBr pellets. The ¹H (300 MHz) and ¹³C (75 MHz) NMR spectra were determined in CDCl₃ (entries 1 and 2) and in *d*₆-DMSO (entries 3–15) on a Bruker AM300L FT NMR spectrometer. The reactions were carried out in a BPL-SANYO microwave oven (BMO-700T).

[†]Dedicated to Professor S. M. Mukherji.

Table 1. Microwave-assisted synthesis of 3,4-dihydropyrimidin-2(1*H*)-ones using oxalic acid as a catalyst in solvent-free condition

Entry	R ¹	R ²	Time (min)	Yield* (%)	M.p. (°C)	Lit. m.p.
1	CH ₃ CH ₂ CH ₂	Et	16	79	152	153–155
2	(CH ₃) ₂ CH	Et	13	81	171–172	170–172
3	C ₆ H ₅	Et	15	91	202–203	202–204
4	4-(Cl)C ₆ H ₄	Et	14	80	216	215–216
5	3-(Br)C ₆ H ₄	Et	12	81	185	185–186
6	4-(CH ₃ O)C ₆ H ₄	Et	17	90	201	201–202
7	3-(NO ₂)C ₆ H ₄	Et	11	89	226–227	226–227.5
8	4-(NO ₂)C ₆ H ₄	Et	13	88	206–207	207–208.5
9	4-(NMe ₂)C ₆ H ₄	Et	18	90	255–257	256–257
10	3,4-(CH ₃ O) ₂ C ₆ H ₃	Et	19	88	176	178–178.5
11	3-(CH ₃ O)-4-(OH)C ₆ H ₃	Et	23	90	230–232	232–233
12	3,4-(OCH ₂ O)C ₆ H ₃	Et	16	85	187	187–188
13	C ₆ H ₅	Me	14	88	208–210	209–212
14	4-(CH ₃ O)C ₆ H ₄	Me	16	92	190–192	192–194
15	4-(NO ₂)C ₆ H ₄	Me	17	84	236–237	235–237

*Isolated yields.

Table 2. IR, ¹H NMR and ¹³C NMR spectral data of 3,4-dihydropyrimidin-2(1*H*)-ones

Entry	IR cm ⁻¹	¹ H NMR δ ppm	¹³ C NMR δ ppm
1	3352, 3250, 3120, 2954, 1712, 1646, 1230, 1092	8.82 (1H, s), 7.25 (1H, s), 4.06 (1H, s), 4.00 (2H, q, <i>J</i> 6.9 Hz), 2.10 (3H, s), 1.37–1.39 (4H, m), 1.12 (3H, t, <i>J</i> 7.0 Hz), 0.78 (3H, t, <i>J</i> 7.0 Hz)	165.7 (C), 153.2 (C), 148.1 (C), 99.9 (C), 59.3 (CH ₂), 50.0 (CH), 45.2 (CH ₂), 23.7 (CH ₃), 21.2 (CH), 18.5 (CH ₃), 14.3 (CH ₃)
2	3241, 3120, 2961, 1725, 1645, 1287, 1231	8.26 (1H, s), 6.03 (1H, s), 4.22 (1H, s), 4.15 (2H, q, <i>J</i> 7.1 Hz), 2.27 (3H, s), 1.84 (1H, m), 1.26 (3H, t, <i>J</i> 7.1 Hz), 0.90 (3H, d, <i>J</i> 6.9 Hz), 0.85 (3H, d, <i>J</i> 6.8 Hz)	166.2 (C), 154.9 (C), 146.8 (C), 100.5 (C), 59.8 (CH ₂), 57.1 (CH), 34.5 (CH), 18.4 (CH ₃), 15.7 (CH ₃), 14.3 (CH ₃)
3	3242, 3116, 2974, 1706, 1646, 1221, 1090	9.12 (1H, s), 7.68 (1H, s), 7.28–7.21 (5H, m), 5.11 (1H, s), 3.94 (2H, q, <i>J</i> 6.9 Hz), 2.21 (3H, s), 1.05 (3H, t, <i>J</i> 6.9 Hz)	165.5 (C), 152.3 (C), 148.3 (C), 144.9 (C), 128.5 (2CH), 127.4 (CH), 126.3 (2CH), 99.6 (C), 59.3 (CH ₂), 54.1 (CH), 17.7 (CH ₃), 14.1 (CH ₃)
4	3242, 3115, 2980, 1704, 1649, 1489, 1221, 1091	9.20 (1H, s), 7.74 (1H, s), 7.34 (2H, d, <i>J</i> 8.5 Hz), 7.21 (2H, d, <i>J</i> 8.5 Hz), 5.12 (1H, d, <i>J</i> 2.9 Hz), 3.93 (2H, q, <i>J</i> 7.0 Hz), 2.22 (3H, s), 1.04 (3H, t, <i>J</i> 7.0 Hz)	165.3 (C), 152.1 (C), 148.7 (C), 143.8 (C), 131.9 (C), 128.4 (CH), 128.3 (CH), 99.1 (C), 59.4 (CH ₂), 53.6 (CH), 17.9 (CH ₃), 14.1 (CH ₃)
5	3416, 3228, 3113, 2976, 2932, 1705, 1654, 1613, 1589	9.20 (1H, s), 7.74 (1H, s), 7.34 (2H, d, <i>J</i> 8.5 Hz), 7.21 (2H, d, <i>J</i> 8.5 Hz), 5.12 (1H, d, <i>J</i> 2.9 Hz), 3.93 (2H, q, <i>J</i> 7.0 Hz), 2.22 (3H, s), 1.04 (3H, t, <i>J</i> 7.0 Hz)	165.3 (C), 152.1 (C), 148.7 (C), 143.8 (C), 131.9 (C), 128.4 (CH), 128.3 (CH), 99.1 (C), 59.4 (CH ₂), 53.6 (CH), 17.9 (CH ₃), 14.1 (CH ₃)
6	3241, 3111, 2974, 1704, 1648, 1223, 1089	9.08 (1H, s), 7.61 (1H, s), 7.14 (2H, d, <i>J</i> 8.5 Hz), 6.83 (2H, d, <i>J</i> 8.5 Hz), 5.05 (1H, d, <i>J</i> 2.9 Hz), 3.93 (2H, q, <i>J</i> 7.0 Hz), 3.67 (3H, s), 2.19 (3H, s), 1.05 (3H, t, <i>J</i> 7.0 Hz)	165.5 (C), 158.5 (C), 152.3 (C), 148.0 (C), 137.1 (C), 127.5 (CH), 113.8 (CH), 99.8 (C), 59.4 (CH ₂), 55.0 (CH ₃), 53.4 (CH), 17.8 (CH ₃), 14.2 (CH ₃)

(Table-2 contd.)

7	3328, 3217, 3090, 2964, 1706, 1625, 1528, 1349, 1221, 1087	9.21 (1H, s), 8.07 (1H, d, <i>J</i> 7.8 Hz), 7.99 (1H, s), 7.82 (1H, s), 7.61 (2H, m), 5.28 (1H, s), 2.20 (3H, s), 1.01 (3H, t, <i>J</i> 7.0 Hz)	165.4 (C), 152.2 (C), 149.2 (C), 147.8 (C), 146.7 (C), 133.1 (CH), 130.4 (CH), 122.5 (CH), 121.0 (CH), 98.9 (C), 59.8 (CH ₂), 53.7 (CH), 17.8 (CH ₃), 13.9 (CH ₃)
8	3377, 3235, 2977, 1704, 1641, 1521, 1348, 1216, 1092	9.32 (1H, s), 8.28 (2H, d, <i>J</i> 8.4 Hz), 7.89 (1H, s), 7.63 (2H, d, <i>J</i> 8.4 Hz), 5.26 (1H, d, <i>J</i> 3.2 Hz), 3.94 (2H, q, <i>J</i> 7.2 Hz), 2.28 (3H, s), 1.07 (3H, t, <i>J</i> 7.2 Hz)	165.2 (C), 151.9 (C), 149.3 (C), 146.8 (C), 127.7 (CH), 123.8 (CH), 98.4 (C), 59.5 (CH ₂), 53.6 (CH), 17.9 (CH), 14.0 (CH ₃)
9	3242, 3116, 2974, 1706, 1646, 1221, 1090	9.12 (1H, s), 7.68 (1H, s), 7.28–7.21 (4H, m), 5.11 (1H, s), 3.94 (2H, q, <i>J</i> 6.9 Hz), 2.83 (6H, s), 2.21 (3H, s), 1.05 (3H, t, <i>J</i> 6.9 Hz)	165.5 (C), 152.3 (C), 148.3 (C), 144.9 (C), 128.5 (2CH), 127.4 (CH), 126.3 (2CH), 99.6 (C), 59.3 (CH ₂), 54.1 (CH), 17.7 (CH ₃), 14.1 (CH ₃)
10	3346, 3241, 2938, 1702, 1655, 1513, 1263, 1226	8.88 (1H, s), 7.26 (1H, s), 6.86 (2H, m), 6.66 (1H, d, <i>J</i> 6.9 Hz), 5.08 (1H, d, <i>J</i> 2.9 Hz), 3.91 (2H, q, <i>J</i> 7.0 Hz), 3.62 (3H, s), 3.60 (3H, s), 2.16 (3H, s), 0.98 (3H, t, <i>J</i> 7.0 Hz)	166.2 (C), 153.0 (C), 148.3 (C), 148.0 (C), 147.8 (C), 136.9 (C), 118.3 (CH), 111.7 (CH), 110.2 (CH), 100.3 (C), 59.9 (CH ₂), 56.5 (CH ₃), 17.6 (CH ₃), 13.8 (CH ₃)
11	3243, 3115, 2936, 1701, 1645, 1222, 1090	9.04 (1H, s), 8.96 (1H, s), 7.58 (1H, s), 6.76 (1H, s), 6.66 (2H, d, <i>J</i> 8.0 Hz), 6.57 (2H, d, <i>J</i> 8.0 Hz), 5.03 (1H, s), 3.95 (2H, q, <i>J</i> 6.9 Hz), 3.68 (3H, s), 2.20 (3H, s), 1.06 (3H, t, <i>J</i> 6.9 Hz)	165.6 (C), 152.4 (C), 147.8 (C), 142.4 (C), 136.0 (C), 118.4 (CH), 115.4 (CH), 111.1 (CH), 99.9 (C), 59.3 (CH ₂), 55.7 (CH ₃), 53.7 (CH), 17.8 (CH ₃), 14.2 (CH ₃)
12	3355, 3222, 3105, 2968, 1700, 1640, 1229, 1092	9.16 (1H, s), 7.66 (1H, s), 6.83 (1H, d, <i>J</i> 8.0 Hz), 6.73 (1H, s), 6.67 (1H, d, <i>J</i> 8.0 Hz), 5.96 (2H, s), 5.05 (1H, d, <i>J</i> 3.2 Hz), 3.97 (2H, q, <i>J</i> 7.2 Hz), 2.23 (3H, s), 1.09 (3H, t, <i>J</i> 7.2 Hz)	165.6 (C), 152.3 (C), 148.2 (C), 147.3 (C), 146.5 (C), 138.9 (C), 119.3 (CH), 108.1 (CH), 106.7 (CH), 101.0 (CH ₂), 99.7 (C), 59.4 (CH ₂), 53.8 (CH), 17.9 (CH ₃), 14.1 (CH ₃)
13	3332, 3226, 3107, 2947, 1695, 1665, 1413, 1237, 1092	9.24 (1H, s), 7.66 (1H, s), 7.25–7.18 (5H, m), 5.13 (1H, s), 3.45 (3H, s), 2.19 (3H, s)	166.4 (C), 152.2 (C), 148.4 (C), 144.1 (C), 128.7 (2CH), 127.7 (CH), 126.2 (2CH), 99.8 (C), 53.9 (CH ₂), 51.1 (CH), 17.8 (CH ₃)
14	3245, 3112, 2950, 1715, 1652, 1438, 1238, 1095	9.11 (1H, s), 7.64 (1H, s), 7.10 (2H, d, <i>J</i> 7.9 Hz), 6.83 (2H, d, <i>J</i> 7.9 Hz), 5.06 (1H, s), 3.72 (3H, s), 3.52 (3H, s), 2.24 (3H, s)	166.1 (C), 158.6 (C), 152.3 (C), 148.3 (C), 136.9 (C), 127.4 (2CH), 113.9 (2CH), 99.6 (C), 55.2 (CH ₃), 53.3 (CH), 50.9 (CH ₃), 17.8 (CH ₃)
15	3364, 3225, 3113, 2955, 1708, 1640, 1517, 1227, 1094	9.41 (1H, s), 8.22 (2H, d, <i>J</i> 8.4 Hz), 7.93 (1H, s), 7.51 (2H, d, <i>J</i> 8.4 Hz), 5.27 (1H, d, <i>J</i> 2.8 Hz), 3.54 (3H, s), 2.27 (3H, s)	165.8 (C), 151.5 (C), 149.5 (C), 146.8 (C), 127.7 (CH), 123.9 (CH), 98.4 (C), 53.6 (CH ₃), 51.3 (CH), 17.9 (CH ₃)

General procedure : Ethyl/methyl acetoacetate (2.5 mmol), aldehyde (2.5 mmol), urea (3.75 mmol) and oxalic acid dihydrate (1 mmol) were mixed thoroughly. The mixture was taken in a 100 ml Erlenmeyer flask, placed in an alumina bath inside a microwave oven and irradiated at 600 watt for the specified time period (Table 1). The solid product was removed from the oven, poured into crushed ice (20 g), stirred for several minutes and filtered. The solid residue was washed with cold water several times and recrystallised from ethanol. All the products were characterized by IR, ¹H and ¹³C NMR spectroscopic analyses and by comparison with

m.ps. of the reported compounds (Tables 1 and 2).

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